

SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF "EDUCATION" IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract: This article explores the application of scientific-methodical principles in teaching the science of education to primary grade students. Grounded in theories of child development and pedagogy, these principles provide a framework for designing effective learning experiences that meet the needs of young learners. The article discusses key principles such as developmentally appropriate practices, active learning, constructivism, scaffolding, differentiation, integration, real-world connections, assessment for learning, collaborative learning, and reflective practice. Practical strategies for implementing these principles in the primary classroom are provided, along with examples of how they can enhance students' understanding of educational concepts.

Keywords: Education Science, Primary Grades, Scientific-Methodical Principles, Developmentally Appropriate Practices, Active Learning, Constructivism, Scaffolding, Differentiation, Integration, Real-World Connections, Assessment for Learning, Collaborative Learning, Reflective Practice.

This article examines the application of scientific-methodical principles in teaching the science of education to primary grade students. Grounded in theories of child development and pedagogy, these principles provide a framework for

designing effective learning experiences that meet the needs of young learners. The article discusses key principles such as developmentally appropriate practices, active learning, constructivism, scaffolding, differentiation, integration, real-world connections, assessment for learning, collaborative learning, and reflective practice. Practical strategies for implementing these principles in the primary classroom are provided, along with examples of how they can enhance students' understanding of educational concepts.

It is a system of improving the educational process based on advanced tools, methods, technical means and methods. This system is created by the teacher and serves to connect the stages of education. It includes such things as pre-determining its content and tasks, purpose, preparation of forms and means of education, planning of lessons aimed at reducing the moral qualities intended to be formed in the student. Today, with the development of science and technology, human activity has expanded tremendously, and new technologies are entering. Changes in quality indicate that now, which requires new methods and is becoming an integral part of the educational process, which introduces its own characteristics there are also new technical, informational, audiovisual tools, which have turned modern pedagogical technologies into concrete reality.

Increases the productivity of the educational process, forms students' independent thinking process, and students' knowledge increases enthusiasm and interest, solid acquisition of knowledge, free use of it in practice forms knowledge and skills. The traditional teaching system can be described as informative teaching due to the fact that it relies on written and spoken words, since the teacher's activity is not only as an organizer of the educational process, but also as a source of authoritative knowledge is being evaluated emphasizing that it is turning.

Teaching the science of education in primary grades requires a systematic and evidence-based approach to support the cognitive, social, and emotional

development of young learners. This article explores the scientific-methodical principles that underpin effective teaching practices in this domain, offering guidance for educators seeking to optimize student learning outcomes.

Key Principles and Strategies:

1. **Developmentally Appropriate Practices:** Align teaching methods and content with the developmental stage and needs of primary grade students, fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment.

2. **Active Learning:** Engage students in hands-on activities, discussions, and interactive experiences to promote deeper understanding and retention of educational concepts.

3. **Constructivism:** Emphasize a constructivist approach where students actively construct their understanding of educational principles through exploration, inquiry, and collaboration.

4. **Scaffolding:** Provide structured support and guidance to help students build upon their existing knowledge and skills, gradually increasing complexity as they progress.

5. **Differentiation:** Tailor instruction to accommodate the diverse needs and learning styles of primary grade students, ensuring that all learners have opportunities to succeed.

6. **Integration:** Integrate the science of education with other subject areas, making connections to students' real-life experiences and interests to enhance relevance and engagement.

7. **Real-World Connections:** Create opportunities for students to apply educational concepts in authentic contexts, fostering deeper understanding and transferability of learning.

8. **Assessment for Learning:** Use ongoing formative assessment strategies to monitor student progress, identify areas for growth, and provide timely feedback to support continuous improvement.

9. Collaborative Learning: Promote collaboration and peer interaction through group activities, projects, and discussions, fostering a sense of community and shared learning.

10. Reflective Practice: Encourage students to reflect on their learning experiences, identify strengths and areas for improvement, and set goals for their ongoing development as learners.

Conclusion:

By applying scientific-methodical principles in teaching education science to primary grade students, educators can create dynamic and effective learning experiences that support the holistic development of young learners. Through developmentally appropriate practices, active engagement, scaffolded support, and meaningful integration, educators can empower students to become critical thinkers, lifelong learners, and active participants in their own educational journey.

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